

Semantic Interoperability: PIDs, RO-Crates & Nanopublications

In the FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) landscape, PIDs, RO-Crates and nanopublications represent three different approaches to making digital objects FAIR and machine-actionable.

They roughly correspond to the following three paradigms:

- PIDs are infrastructure-centric. FDO behavior and FAIRness are implemented primarily by trusted repositories.
- RO-Crates are self-describing, object-centric. FAIRness is implemented through persistent identifier systems with structured kernel metadata. This approach is strongly associated with the FDO specifications promoted by the Research Data Alliance and FDO Forum.
- Nanopublications are fine-grained, semantic web-centric. The FAIR Digital Object is implemented as a self-describing web-native object, often using linked data standards.

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

A persistent identifier (PID) is a globally unique identifier that can be used to locate a digital object. Common examples include DOI, Handle and ARK. In discussions about the FDO, a PID is more than just a link — it can carry structured kernel metadata that makes the object machine-actionable.

- Stable and durable
- Machine-resolvable
- Infrastructure-level trust
- Strong alignment with formal FDO specifications

- Needs governance and infrastructure
- Kernel metadata must stay minimal
- Doesn't define internal object packaging

Research Object Crate (RO-Crate)

An RO-Crate (Research Object Crate) is a lightweight, self-describing package for research data and metadata. It typically consists of a folder (or archive), data files, a 'ro-crate-metadata.json' file and metadata expressed in JSON-LD (Linked Data format). It is essentially a web-native, self-contained FAIR package.

- Self-contained
- Web-native
- Easy to implement
- Strong semantic flexibility

- No inherent persistence guarantee
- Governance varies
- Machine automation depends on consistent vocabularies

Nanopublications

A Nanopublication is a very small, machine-readable scientific statement with explicit provenance. Each nanopublication consists of three RDF graphs: Assertion (the core claim), Provenance (how we know it), Publication info (authorship, timestamp). It is designed for the semantic web and knowledge graphs.

- Fine-grained machine reasoning
- Explicit provenance
- Cryptographic integrity possible
- Highly composable

- Steeper learning curve
- RDF expertise required
- Harder for large file-based data

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